

CHARACTERIZATION OF CONTINUOUS GLASS FIBRE-REINFORCED POLYPROPYLENE

Edith Mäder, Dieter Voigt and Liane Häußler
Institute of Polymer Research, Hohe Str. 6, 01069 Dresden, Germany

ABSTRACT

In this study the interphase properties of differently sized glass fibres and both non-modified and chemically modified polypropylene matrices of different melt viscosities and after different thermal treatment have been studied. As experimental techniques, size exclusion chromatography (SEC), differential scanning calorimetry (DSC), single-fibre pull-out test and mechanical testing of continuous fibre-reinforced polypropylenes have been used.

In single-fibre tests the influence of molecular parameters, matrix modification, and sizing on the interfacial shear strength has been detected. In final composite properties these influences were overlapped by the impregnation caused by the conditions of composite production.

INTRODUCTION

The aim of our research work is to develop new material combinations and processing methods which can be used to compete with mass production of sheet metal parts, SMC/RTM and GMT on performance/price and performance/weight basis.

It is known that the impregnation of fibres by thermoplastic melts is more difficult than by resins and depends on the molecular characteristics of the polypropylenes. In order to characterize the influence of these properties on the transfer of stresses between matrix and reinforcing fibres different sized glass fibres and both non-modified and chemically modified polypropylene matrices have been studied.

It is well known that the mechanical properties of fibre-reinforced composites are influenced by the surface treatment (sizing) of the reinforcing fibres [1, 2]. The thickness of these sizings is in the range of 0.5 to 1.0 μm for commercially available glass fibres with diameters between 10 and 14 μm . Generally, the sizings consist of 80-90 wt-% polymeric binder, 5-10 wt-% silane coupling agents and 5-10 wt-% auxiliary agents.

The function of the silane coupling agents and their interactions with both glass fibres and polymer have been reviewed by Ishida [3]. The generated silanol groups react with the glass surface primarily via hydrogen bonds to form partly covalent bonds.

The second functionality of the sizing consists in its ability to interact with the thermoplastic or thermosetting resin by a chemical reaction.

In earlier publications, it was shown that the interfacial shear strength can be improved by the application of modified polypropylene in short [4, 5] and continuous fibre-reinforced polypropylenes [6].

It could also be proved that for the interphase formation not only the silane coupling agent is important. Because of the extreme sensitivity to abrasion and bending of the reinforcing fibres, the sizing must also fulfil processing requirements, whereby it can rather influence the frictional behaviour.

Further it could be demonstrated that the polymeric binder plays a crucial role in the interphase formation as reported about different model sizings. Direct fibre/melt wetting experiments have been provided evidence to chemical reactions together with interdiffusion effects in the interphase between sized glass fibres and the modified polypropylene matrices [7].

Presently it is still difficult to characterize the influence of molecular parameters on the interphase formation in model composites under conditions comparable to processing conditions as fibre-polymer melt interaction, the influence of molecular parameters on the macromechanical composite properties, and the correlation of micro- or mesomechanical interphase parameter with the composite properties.

The topic of this study is to investigate the interphase properties of glass fibre-PP model composites using differently sized (polymeric film formers) glass fibres and PP matrices, which were non-polar or chemically coupled. Different polypropylenes have been used to study the influence of molecular parameters on the micro- and macromechanical properties of composites.

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIAL

The materials used in this study were specially sized glass fibres and both polypropylene filaments and films made at the spinning or extrusion equipment in the Institute of Polymer Research. The sizings (silane coupling agents, film former) of the glass fibres are listed in *Table 3*.

Four PP-grades of different melt viscosities *PP3*, *PP13*, *PP25*, *PP36* (numbers represent the melt flow index values determined by 230°C, 21.6 N [MFI 230/2.16]) were studied. As commercial modifier *M1* a maleic anhydride grafted PP has been blended with the non-polar polypropylenes in an amount of 2 wt.-% during filament formation or film extrusion. The different polypropylene states (different annealing) were described as */0 granules*, */1 extruded film*, */2 split-film*, */3 hot pressed*.

Commingled yarns were made from *PP25* and *PP25/M1* and E-glass filaments *F*. *PP3/M1*, *PP13/M1*, and *PP36/M1* were used to extrude films. Split-films were produced from the extruded films and also combined with E-glass filaments *F*. Continuous fibre-reinforced UD-plates for mechanical testing were produced from commingled yarns and side-by-side ordered glass filaments and split-films by correct unidirectional winding and afterwards hot pressing under identical conditions (220 °C, 5 min, 3 MPa).

SEC

The SEC measurements were performed with a high temperature GPC (KNAUER) equipped with a trimodal kit of ZORBAX PSM columns. TCB (1,2,4-trichlorobenzene) with addition of 0.1% (w/v) biphenylamine as antioxidant was used as mobile phase at 145 °C. The injected volume was 0.100 ml, the concentration of polymer was 0.25 % (w/v). The sample solutions were filtered using a self-made internal device in the column oven. For calculation of the molecular mass of the PP-samples the columns calibration was established by means of a linear polyethylene of known molecular weight distribution.

DSC

The thermal behaviour was studied by means of DSC 7 (Perkin-Elmer) in the temperature range of -60 to 210 °C in nitrogen atmosphere at a heating and cooling rate of 10 K/min. The sample weight was about 5 mg.

To produce a unique thermal prehistory the samples were heated to 210 °C and than cooled down. The crystallization behaviour was investigated in order to show the influence of modified PP in comparison to unmodified ones.

SINGLE-FIBRE PULL-OUT TEST

Single fibre model composites of the glass fibres and matrix polypropylenes were prepared to measure the debonding shear strength (or interfacial shear strength IFSS) by single fibre pull-out tests. The pull-out tests were carried out by the pull-out apparatus [1] which allows high precision fibre displacement and force measurements of end-embedded fibres. The fibres were embedded at 230 °C under argon atmosphere, embedding lengths between 50 and 300 µm and heating/cooling rates of about 50 K/min. The pull-out test was carried out with identical velocities of pulling out the fibres ($0.2 \mu\text{m s}^{-1}$) at ambient temperature. From each force-displacement-curve (e. g. Figure 1) the force at debonding F_d and the embedded length l_e are determined and the interfacial shear strength τ_d is calculated. The fibre diameter D is measured microscopically.

About 15 to 20 single tests were used to calculate the mean value of each fibre/polymer combination. The force at debonding and the embedded length were determined from each force-displacement curve and IFSS was calculated.

Figure 1. Comparison of the force-displacement curves of PP25 and PP25/M1 with sizing D

COMPOSITE TESTING

The plates were cut up in test specimens to carry out the following tests (schemes of loading cf. Table 4):

- three-point bending test, and short-beam bending test to calculate interlaminar shear strength ILSS(DIN 29 971)
- shear test (compression loading)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 2 demonstrates the results of crystallization in dependence on sample state for example of PP 13. The unmodified film shows an increase in onset temperature ($T_{c,o}$) and maximum temperature ($T_{c,m}$) in comparison to granules and the shape of the curve becomes smaller. This effect seems to be caused by the stabilization of PP for preparation of the films. The weight loss measured after procedure in the DSC decreases from 0.3 ... 0.4 % for the granules to ≤ 0.1 % for stabilized films.

The modification of PP leads to a further increase in crystallization temperatures. That means the modifier acts as nucleating agent. In comparison to the initial granules the crystallization is accelerated. The value $\Delta T_c = (T_{c,o} - T_{c,m})$ as measure of crystallization rate decreases. This behaviour was found for all studied PP-samples and the corresponding values are listed in Table 1.

Figure 2. Crystallization curves of PP 13
 — initial granules (PP 13/0),
 - - - unmodified film (PP 13/1)
 - • - modified film (PP 13/M 1/1)

Table 1. Crystallization temperatures of various PP samples

Sample identification	T _{c,o} (°C)	T _{c,m} (°C)	ΔT _c (°C)
Modifier M1	120.4	115.5	4.9
PP 3/0	114.2	107.4	6.8
PP 3/1	116.8	112.7	4.1
PP 3/M1/1	123.4	119.4	4.0
PP 13/0	117.0	110.8	6.2
PP 13/1	117.0	111.8	5.2
PP 13/M1/1	122.1	117.5	4.6
PP 36/0	121.3	115.3	6.0
PP 36/M1/1	124.0	118.4	5.6

In an earlier publication, it could be shown that the surfaces of glass fibres act as further nucleating agents and a shift of the onset temperature of the crystallization to higher values occurred. Significant differences between unsized and sized fibres were not observed [7].

A direct heat of reaction measured by DSC between fibre and matrix during composite formation could not be detected [7].

However, by means of very sensitive direct fibre/polypropylene melt wetting measurements [7] it was assumed that this behaviour can be due to the expected strong acid-base interaction between the basic amine groups of the sizing and the acidic groups of the modified PP melt leading to a chemical reaction in the interphase. A further evidence for this conclusion is the completely different wetting kinetics of the untreated glass fibres with the modified PP melt.

In the following Table 2 the results of molecular weight distribution obtained by SEC-measurements are listed. The number-, weight-, and z-average molecular weights were calculated from the distribution (MWD). These results show small differences in molecular weight averages of the modifier M1 and the PP13/0. A comparison of the distribution curves of M1 and PP13/0 (Figure 3, 4) clearly detects a higher polydispersity of M1. For all samples no significant dependences of MWD on sample preparation (degradation) could be detected. The small differences could be caused by heterogeneity of sample material.

Table 2: Results of molecular weight distribution obtained by SEC-measurements

Sample identification	M _n 10 ⁻⁴ g/mol	M _w 10 ⁻⁵ g/mol	M _z 10 ⁻⁵ g/mol
M1	2.03	1.69	5.39
PP3/0	4.17	2.19	6.61
PP13/0	2.20	1.59	5.02
PP13/M1/1	2.50	1.54	4.23
PP13/M1/2	2.54	1.63	4.84
PP13/M1/3	2.10	1.47	4.14
PP36/0	1.77	1.43	3.90
PP36/M1/1	2.37	1.50	3.72
PP36/M1/2	2.07	1.55	4.11
PP36/M1/3	2.27	1.44	3.51

Fig. 3. Molecular weight distribution of the selected PP13/0 in comparison to the pure modifier

Fig. 4. Cumulative weight fraction of the selected PP13/0 in comparison to the pure modifier

To study the results of physical and chemical interaction of the polymer melt with differently sized glass fibres single-fibre pull-out tests have been carried out with model composites of the differently sized glass fibres as well as modified and unmodified PP 25. The PP 25 was selected because of the mean melt viscosity. The interfacial shear strengths are calculated as

characterization of fibre-matrix adhesion from the force-displacement curves. Generally, the interfacial shear strengths of sized glass fibres with modified polypropylenes were determined higher than with unmodified ones. Different sizings show lower changes in the IFSS. This effect is not only due to the silane coupling agent (Table 3, cf. unmodified glass fibre, glass fibre without film former) but can be concluded by a combination with the polymeric binder (e. g. PP/PU dispersion) to contribute to a better compatibility with the polymer matrix than, for example, the used epoxy dispersion in sizing E. Comparing the differences in IFSS with the different wetting kinetics it can be concluded that sizing E inhibits the complete spreading of PP 25/M1 more than sizing D due to the compatibility of the polymeric film former with the polymer matrix resulting in lower IFSS as published elsewhere [7].

Table 3. Interfacial shear strengths (IFSS) of PP and PPM with different sized glass fibres

Polymer	Sizing	Silane coupling agents	Film former	IFSS [MPa]
PP 25	A	---	---	5.9 ± 0.6
PP 25	B	Aminosilane	---	5.2 ± 0.4
PP 25	C	Amino/vinyl-silane	PE dispersion	5.3 ± 0.5
PP 25	D	Aminosilane	PE/PUR dispersion	6.7 ± 0.9
PP 25	E	Aminosilane	Epoxy dispersion	6.0 ± 1.0
PP 25	F	A 1100	PP/PUR dispersion	7.2 ± 1.5
PP 25	G	A 1100	PP dispersion	7.2 ± 0.9
PP 25/M1	A	---	---	8.6 ± 2.6
PP 25/M1	D	Aminosilane	PE/PUR dispersion	11.6 ± 1.4
PP 25/M1	E	Aminosilane	Epoxy dispersion	6.6 ± 0.3
PP 25/M1	F	A 1100	PP/PUR dispersion	11.9 ± 2.2
PP 25/M1	G	A 1100	PP dispersion	12.4 ± 3.5

Table 4. Properties of UD-composites produced by film stacking or from commingled yarns

Sample identification PP/Glass Sizing	IFSS [MPa]	Shear strength [MPa]	Interlaminar shear strength [MPa]	3-Point bending strength [MPa]
<i>film stacking</i>				
PP3 M1/F	10.9 ± 1.2	11.4	*)	*)
PP13 M1/F	14.3 ± 2.0	9.1	13.4	*)
PP36 M1/F	15.8 ± 2.3	10.8	13.9	293.8
<i>commingled yarn</i>				
PP25/F	7.2 ± 1.5	11.0	*)	245.5
PP25 M1/F	11.9 ± 2.2	19.7	18.7	434.4

*) no delamination, no fracture due to the bad impregnation

Both unmodified and modified PP 25 represent the highest IFSS-values of the compared sizings if the sizings F and G were used. Because of a better processing behaviour the sizing F is used to produce unidirectional composites with the different studied polypropylenes.

The fibre-matrix adhesion of the real composites was studied in comparison to the single-fibre pull-out test (Table 4). The data show that the micro as well as the macromechanical properties of glass fibre-PP composites are influenced by the matrix modification that leads to a strong chemical bonding in the interphase. Increasing melt flow indices (MFI) result in a slight increase in the interfacial shear strengths. However, differences in the mechanical properties in dependence on the MFI could not be detected. Table 4 shows that only the PP36 (MFI 230/2.16: 36 g/10 min) could be used to produce a composite by film stacking. Although the MFI is higher than that of the PP used in composite consolidation by commingled yarn the determined shear strength, interlaminar shear strength, and three point bending strength are poor.

Microphotographs of polished cross-sections provide evidence of poor homogeneity of the composites produced by film stacking due to the bad impregnation. The tested properties of composites produced from commingled yarns with modified PP are better caused by higher homogeneity of fibre/matrix distribution in the preforms and consequently shorter flowing paths.

CONCLUSIONS

It was proved that the chemical interactions in the interphase caused by the chemical modification of the polypropylene matrix and various polymer dispersions of the sizing influence the interfacial shear strengths of the glass fibre-polypropylene composites. The modifier acts as a nucleating agent. The influence of different molecular parameters (melt flow index, molecular weight distribution) on the interfacial shear strength was detected. In final composites the influences of these parameters have been overlapped by the impregnation caused by the conditions of composite production.

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